

Unexpected Diagnosis: Calcified Pulmonary Hydatid Cyst Revealed by Cardiac Injury (Radiological Image)

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OBSERVATION

A 28-year-old patient, a chronic smoker, was admitted to the emergency department for management of a cardiac air wound. Upon initial clinical examination, the patient presented with hemodynamically and respiratorily stable condition, accompanied by a left-sided air effusion syndrome. Echocardiography revealed no anomalies. Subsequently, the patient underwent thoracic angioscanning, which identified a significantly abundant left pneumothorax alongside a calcified cystic lesion in the right lower lobe (Figure 1 and 2).

Figure 1: non-contrast CT section showing a calcified hydatid cyst in the right lower lobe

Figure 2: CT section showing a large left pneumothorax

The patient underwent pleural drainage, resulting in lung re-expansion against the thoracic wall. Subsequent scheduling included resection of the cystic lesion. Pathological examination outcomes confirmed the presence of a calcified pulmonary hydatid cyst.

DISCUSSION

The calcification of pulmonary hydatid cysts, an exceedingly rare phenomenon, prompts profound inquiries into its underlying mechanisms and its impact on clinical management.^[1] The uncommon discovery of calcifications within a pulmonary hydatid cyst raises questions regarding the involved pathophysiological processes. Although several hypotheses have been proposed, the precise mechanism of calcification remains enigmatic.

While the clinical management of calcified pulmonary hydatid cysts remains similar to that of non-calcified cysts, understanding these mechanisms opens crucial avenues for future research. The frequent serendipitous discovery of calcification cases during medical imaging examinations underscores the importance of a multidisciplinary approach to such exceptional presentations.^[2,3]

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